

Horizon Europe Cluster 3 - Fight against Crime and Terrorism 2026 - Analysis

Context

The 2026 Fight against Crime and Terrorism (FCT) call represents a strategic investment of €40.67 million across six specialised research topics. Guided by the ProtectEU Internal Security Strategy and the Preparedness Union Strategy, the call focuses on modernising law enforcement capabilities against evolving threats.

Opening Date: 06 May 2026

Deadline: 05 Nov 2026

Total Topics: 6

Cluster 3 FCT : EUCS Taxonomy - Policy Coverage

Cluster 3 FCT : EUCS Taxonomy - Functions Coverage

Comparative snapshot: 2014-24 to 2026

- Continuity:** Investigation and Forensics remains the top function, mirroring the decade-long trend identified in ENACT Analytical Report 01
- Novelty:** The "Climate-Crime Nexus" (FCT-01) is a significant new priority, addressing how environmental changes create opportunistic criminal patterns - a shift from traditional policy focuses.

Cross-cutting themes

- Social Sciences (SSH):** Strong emphasis on the "Human Factor." Topics FCT-01, FCT-04, and FCT-05 explicitly require the effective contribution of SSH disciplines to enhance societal impact.
- Practitioner Involvement:** Mandatory. Every 2026 topic requires the active participation of at least 2 to 3 Police Authorities as beneficiaries to ensure innovation uptake.
- Technology Readiness Level (TRL):**
 - Research-Heavy: FCT-01, 02, 04, and 06 (TRL 4-5) → maturing new knowledge.
 - Innovation-Heavy: FCT-03 and 05 (TRL 6-8) → validating tools in real-world settings.

Cluster 3 FCT : EUCS Taxonomy - Technology Coverage

Horizon Europe Cluster 3: FCT Topic Analysis

Topic	FCT-01	FCT-02	FCT-03	FCT-04	FCT-05	FCT-06
EUCST Primary policy areas	Environmental crime	Crosscutting	Trafficking of humans; Child Sexual Abuse	Drug trafficking; Organised crime	Protection of public spaces; Radicalisation	CBRN Threats; Protection of public spaces
EUCST Secondary policy areas	Trafficking of goods; Cargo crime; Illegal markets	Encryption and 5G	Forensics; Domestic Violence and sexual abuse	Petty crime; Domestic Violence and sexual abuse; youth criminality	Hate speech; Youth criminality	Darknet Illegal markets; Conventional forensics
EUCST Functions	Prevention, response and recovery					●
	Data, information & intelligence	●	●	●		
	Monitoring and surveillance of environments and activities	●			●	●
	Security of information systems, networks and hardware		●			
	Identification and authentication of persons, assets and goods		●	●		
	Detection of goods, substances, assets and people and incidents	●				●
	Investigation and forensics	●	●	●	●	●
	Decontamination and neutralisation					●
	Secure and public communication, data and information exchange		●	●		
	Training and exercises	●	●	●	●	●
EUCST Technologies	Access control/authorisation (building access, system access, etc.)		●		●	
	Data analytics	●	●	●		
	CBRNE detection and neutralisation products					●
	Data storage and exchange		●	●		
	Digital forensics			●		
	General equipment					●
	Internet-based investigation	●	●	●	●	●
	Laboratory equipment for gathering and forensic analysis of samples			●		●
	Healthcare / medical equipment				●	
	Monitoring tools and services				●	
	PPE/Safety equipment					●
	Screening & detection	●				●
	Surveillance systems	●				●
	Training & Simulation	●	●	●	●	●

*This factsheet maps the FCT2026 call topics to the [EU Civil Security Taxonomy \(EUCST\)](#), as per the judgement of ENACT experts